
CSCCE Tech Tip Sheet: Using GitHub for community management

About this tip sheet

In 2023, CSCCE hosted a series of community “Tools Trials” that focused on tools commonly used for community management in open-source and open-source-supporting communities. The goal of the series - which consisted of several live webinars with Q&A and this accompanying tip sheet collection - was to share existing knowledge and provide any scientific community manager with options about tools and use cases they could explore further.

One of the most commonly used tools by open-source communities is GitHub. In this tip sheet, we’ve curated some basic information about GitHub and how you can get started on the platform as a scientific community manager. We’ve also created several case studies describing how different communities are using GitHub, including some of the platform integrations that make their work possible (see page 5 for links to each of these case studies).

What is GitHub?

[GitHub](#) is a version control platform for storing, collaborating on, and tracking projects. It is primarily used for software development, but can also be used for other collaborative work. It uses [Git](#), which is an open-source version control system that can track which users make changes to computer files (e.g., code, documents) and when. Although there are other software platforms that use Git, GitHub is the most popular.

A brief GitHub glossary

[GitHub maintains a full glossary of terms on their website](#), but we’ve summarized a selection of terms that you might find helpful as you consider using GitHub for community engagement.

REPOSITORIES

Repositories, or “repos,” are a collection of files organized into a hierarchy of folders, or “directories.” Alongside the file contents, repos store “metadata,” which includes information such as the author, time of creation and modification, as well as which “commits” a file belongs to.

Commits are the unit of modification of a repository, and are organized into “branches.” One branch is the primary or “default” branch, which contains the canonical state of the repository. By convention this is typically called “main.” Commits contain messages, which are intended to explain what is modified and why.

PULL REQUESTS

Changes are introduced into repositories by “pull requests” (PR’s). Each PR represents a request to add commits from one branch (the “feature branch”) into another branch (usually the default/main branch). It is considered good practice to have systems to check the contents of PRs before they are integrated (or “merged”) – this can be automatic (using continuous integration or “CI” tools) or manual (by requiring file reviews).

ISSUES

To manage what needs to be done on a project, users can organize tasks into “issues.” Each issue is meant to represent a discrete change to the project, such as a new feature, a fix for an existing problem, or a configuration change. Ideally, each issue can be resolved by a single PR, so that merging a PR will close the matching issue.

Issues include descriptions of the change that needs to be made and why, as well as comments to record any discussion of the problem and to debate possible approaches.

ACTIONS

In order to run automated tests or to automate other events, projects need to run code (such as tools that will automatically close old issues). GitHub provides an integrated way to do this called “Actions,” which is popular because it is built into GitHub and free to use for small projects.

Actions will run based on a trigger, such as a PR being created, a comment being added to an issue, a new commit being pushed, or any number of other events. Actions may also run regularly on a defined schedule.

There are predefined actions for most common tasks, including running test suites and building, releasing, and deploying software. Users can add custom actions that can be re-used by others.

ORGANIZATIONS

To manage multiple repositories, a team may create an “organization”, which many GitHub users may belong to. Most real-world projects create an organization and will host their repos under that “namespace” (e.g., the “world-peace” organization might have the “world-peace/love”, “world-peace/happiness” and “world-peace/low-level-bureaucracy” repositories). Each repository will have independent file storage and a separate commit history.

WIKIS

GitHub allows each project repo to have a “wiki.” A wiki is a collection of pages that can be edited inside the GitHub user interface and organized as the project sees fit. Typically, wikis contain documentation and user guides to support the users or the developers of the project.

MARKDOWN

While files in a repo can exist in any format, PRs, issues, and wiki content in GitHub are written in a format called Markdown. Markdown is a good fit for GitHub because it can be read and edited in plain text and displayed in a browser. “GitHub flavored markdown” is the common name for the non-standard set of additions to Markdown that are in use on GitHub, such as checklists and tables.

Why use GitHub?

More often than not, community managers using GitHub for their community are doing so because it is a tool with which at least some of their members are already familiar – perhaps in the context of their jobs or other projects with which they are involved. Members may therefore already be comfortable with the technology, so the barriers to participation are lower. Additional advantages include the fact that GitHub integrates with a number of other platforms and that it lends itself to inviting contributions from community members in an open and transparent way.

WHAT ARE OTHERS USING GITHUB FOR?

While GitHub is primarily used by software developers, there are a number of other uses for the platform that are particularly relevant to community managers in STEM. These include sourcing conference proposals and abstracts (and inviting community member feedback), coordinating the co-creation of community resources, hosting website content and images, and organizing community events (e.g., community calls).

PROS AND CONS OF USING GITHUB FOR COMMUNITY MANAGEMENT

Consideration	Pros	Cons
Familiarity with the platform	If your community members are already familiar with GitHub, using the platform for community management reduces technical barriers to participation.	If GitHub is new to you and/or your members, you'll need to invest significant time in creating scaffolding and setting norms.
Openness and privacy	You can easily create centralized documentation and other materials that members can help maintain and evolve – even using it for their own needs.	It can be challenging to balance public versus private communication and information. For example, what happens if a public conversation needs to be handled privately?
Credit and recognition	Because every issue, PR, and comment in GitHub is associated with a user, contributions are clearly attributed to who did what on a project.	This level of transparency may need to be balanced with privacy, depending on your context and goals.
Transparency and accountability	Anyone can review how changes are made to community files, which adds a layer of accountability.	It is transparent, which means that there is a risk of failing publicly if the repo is not private. This underlines the importance of having strong community guidelines where contributors feel safe.

Accessibility	Anyone with an account can contribute. Issues can be used to make suggestions or have discussions and pull requests can be used to make changes.	If a community member is not already on the platform and not interested in adopting something new, they may not be able to participate in the community in the way they would like.
Customization	Issue templates can be used to standardize member participation so that there are standard formats that are recognizable to both staff and community members.	In some cases, customization may add a barrier to adoption as it requires knowledge of additional features available on the platform, or it introduces different ways of interacting.

Considerations

BEFORE YOU START

Using GitHub does not necessarily require you, as a community manager, to be a proficient software developer. However, if you are not already familiar with the platform, it will take some time to get comfortable with it and the common workflows. Take time to [review this “getting started” guide](#), which may help you decide if this is something you are interested in adopting as a tool for your community.

SCAFFOLDING

Your members will need to know certain key aspects of GitHub to get the most out of it. Consider what kind of scaffolding you will need to provide to ensure your members can contribute to and interact around your shared community project. What this entails will depend on your community (e.g., experienced GitHub users won’t need a primer on how to create a checklist). Useful resources might include a how-to guide, instructional video(s), or a collection of issue templates. If this is the first time that members have used a system with version control and the ability to track work asynchronously and out in the open, you may also need to communicate about how and why this can be useful.

AUTOMATION

One of the things GitHub does really well is to automate tasks that might otherwise be quite time-consuming or tedious. There are GitHub Actions, tasks you schedule to execute when something happens or at a specific time, as well as [a number of bots](#) you can mobilize in repos. Keep in mind that not all tasks that CAN be automated SHOULD be automated - as a community manager there are times when your personal touch will be key.

Getting started on GitHub

You’ll need a GitHub account to create a repo or contribute to existing repos. To create an account, you can follow the steps at <https://github.com/>. Once you have verified your account, you can set up your [profile](#).

To create a new project, you will need to [set up a repo](#). If you are creating a public repo for your community, you will want to include a [license](#) file that specifies how your project can be shared. You can also add contribution guidelines to help community members understand how they can contribute and to set healthy community norms. You may additionally decide to create a private repository to track internal processes or workflows.

GitHub offers [free personal and organizational plans](#), as well as Pro, Team, and Enterprise plans. Free plans have storage limitations, as well as how many actions you can perform per month, and while all features are available for public repositories (encouraging work in the open), they are more limited for private repositories.

Community management on GitHub

The community manager's role in supporting adoption of the platform may include:

- **Setting up the platform** in a way that supports and facilitates contributions from the community
- **Writing a contributor guide** so new contributors have direction on how to get started in contributing to the project
- **Labeling issues into categories** so contributors can easily find relevant issues that match their interests or skillset
- **Reviewing submissions (i.e., pull requests) from the community** and approving those submissions (i.e., merging pull requests)
- **Implementing and enforcing a Code of Conduct** so contributors feel safe engaging on the platform

Team members and community contributors may additionally support each of these tasks.

Case Studies

During our 2023 Tools Trials series, we heard from community managers who are using GitHub for a range of tasks and activities. We've summarized these in the following brief case studies:

- [Using GitHub to manage session proposals for CarpentryCon](#)
- [Using GitHub to plan community calls for rOpenSci](#)
- [Using GitHub to maintain a static website \(CarpentryCon\) or blog \(Data Umbrella\)](#)
- [Using GitHub teams to manage contributor access to Rosetta](#)
- [Using Read the Docs to collaboratively create documentation in GitHub for Zarr](#)
- [Using bots in GitHub to support The Turing Way community](#)

Resources

- [Github Docs](#) - The place to go for help with all things GitHub
- Software Carpentry's [novice GitHub lesson](#)
- GitHub's ["Getting Started" documentation](#)
- Getting started with your GitHub [account](#)

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